

BASIC APPROACHES TO WORKING WITH FAIRY TALE TEXT IN PRIMARY SCHOOL

Jamolova G.J.

1st-year master's student of Angren University

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Abstract. *The main goal of school education is the formation of the student's personality. Reading as a subject has at its disposal such a powerful means of influencing the personality as fiction. Fiction has a huge developmental and educational potential: it introduces the child to the spiritual experience of humanity, develops his mind, and ennobles his feelings. The more deeply and fully a reader perceives a particular work, the greater the impact it has on the personality. Therefore, one of the leading tasks of teaching reading is the task of teaching the perception of a work of art.*

Keywords: *educational value of genres, stories and fairy tales in primary education, children's literature, pedagogy, psychology.*

The problem of aesthetic education of children using fairy tales is especially important for teachers. Aesthetic perception develops as a result of broad acquaintance with fiction, acquisition of necessary knowledge, accumulation of experience and life impressions. Therefore, serious, thoughtful work with fairy tales from the very beginning of introducing a child to literature is so important. The student should name and give examples of: folk and literary fairy tales (everyday, magical, about animals); works of folklore (proverbs and sayings, riddles, fairy tales, tales, legends, traditions, epics); distinguish, compare: works of folklore (riddle, proverb, song, tongue twister), folk and literary fairy tales, genres of children's fiction (fairy tale, story, poem, play, ballad, essays, myths).

These requirements can be met by primary school graduates, provided that they have developed a sufficient range of reading (from works of folklore, as well as classical works of domestic and foreign writers), allowing students not only to name works, give examples of works of different genres of folklore, but also to distinguish them, and be able to indicate their features[1].

We have analyzed the features of the works of Uzbek children's poets and writers. They made a significant contribution to the development of Uzbek children's literary process and they began with the works of the Jadids and progressive poets and writers of the early years[17].

The educational and methodological set of the program meets all these requirements. The textbook on literary reading for grades 1-4 includes works of folklore of the peoples of Russia and other countries of the world. The task of teaching in each grade is to deepen children's knowledge of works of folk art, expand and enrich their reading experience, and introduce literary concepts and ideas. Sections of the textbooks include riddles, proverbs, tongue twisters, nursery rhymes, fairy tales, legends, tales. From grade to grade, the range of reading expands, the level of reading increases. Gradually, children develop concepts of literary (author's) and folk tales, types of tales (magic, everyday, about animals), and comparing tales of the peoples of the world makes it possible to highlight similarities and differences, the "similarity" of plots, the peculiarity of the language of folk and literary tales[2].

Uzbek children's literature began to form from year to year. Especially in these years, the contribution of Z. Diyer, D. Oppokova, M. Fayzi, I. Muslim, A. Rakhmat, Sh. Saadulla, S. Jor, M.

Akilova, K. Muhammadi, H. Nazir was a great event. They encourage children to study well, enjoy the light of science, work hard and grow up as real sons and daughters of their age[16].

New fairy tales are introduced into the third-graders' reading circle, the reading and analysis of which show their unreal world, the existence of positive and negative heroes, the peculiarities of the language of fairy tales of each nation, the presence of repetitions, sayings, beginnings and endings. Third-graders get an idea that the plots of many fairy tales are similar, although they differ in the manner of presentation, since they were created at different times, by different people, in different countries.

In the 4th grade, the reading circle includes fairy tales that are more complex in form and content, which creates conditions for enriching the reading experience, expanding the range of reading, and increasing the level of erudition. Fourth-graders repeat all genres of folklore works and types of fairy tales, study literary fairy tales (B. Tukhliev, S. Matchon, M. Dzhumabayev, etc.). Such a structure of the content of training allows us to constantly expand the range of children's reading, and form basic reading skills[17].

In Uzbek children's poetry of the post-war period, works about the Motherland, the beautiful land, our free country are worthy of attention. It is not enough to list the poems written on this topic: "Yashna, Vatan" (I. Muslim), "Obod ulkam", "Yurtimizning yuragi" (P. Mumin), "Mening Vatanim", "Bakhtli balalar" (K. Hikmat), "Olkamizning tongi" (A. Rakhmat), "The story of a grandfather-farmer and twelve children" (A. Aripov), "The word mother" and others [18].

Let us now consider the requirements for the level of formation of literary concepts and ideas. The mandatory minimum content includes literary propaedeutics of the following concepts:

- genres of works — story, fairy tale (folk or literary), fable, poem, novella, play;
- genres of folklore: riddles, tongue twisters, songs, proverbs and sayings;
- theme of the work;
- main idea;
- plot;
- hero-character, his features, actions;
- writer, author, narrator;
- means of artistic expression in the text — epithets, comparisons

Literary knowledge is necessary for more in-depth work with a work. This knowledge is not given to the student in a ready-made form, but is "discovered" by children in the course of their reading activity [5].

Observations of various forms of fairy tales (folk and literary) lead children to the conclusion that some fairy tales have an unusual introduction or ending in the form of a joke. The selection of fairy tales with sayings and their reading expands the reading range of a beginning reader, enriches speech and reading experience. By selecting jokes, sayings, proverbs for sayings or inventing their own sayings for familiar fairy tales, telling fairy tales with sayings, students learn the world of fairy tales and master the literary concept of "saying"[3].

In the 1st grade: working with text in the 1st grade: practical distinction between a text and a set of sentences; highlighting a paragraph and semantic parts; titling semantic parts, drawing up a schematic or pictorial plan (under the guidance of a teacher).

In the 2nd grade: understanding words and expressions used in the text; distinguishing the simplest cases of polysemy of words and comparisons; dividing the text into parts and making a plan under the guidance of the teacher; determining the main (principal) idea of the work; making

a plan and retelling according to the plan; independent work on assignments and questions about the text of the work.

In the 3rd grade: understanding the sequence and meaning of events; identifying the main idea of the text; knowledge of the structure of the text: beginning, development of the action, ending; drawing up a plan and retelling the content of the text (in detail and selectively) according to the plan and independently, independent completion of assignments for the text[4].

In the 4th grade: understanding and explaining the meanings of words and expressions; drawing up a plan for a story or fairy tale; detailed, brief and selective retelling of the text according to the plan; creative retelling (changes in the narrator's face).

The tasks involve primary and secondary perception of the work. Primary perception reflects the general, mainly emotional impression of what has been read; secondary perception provides reflection on the work. For organizing primary perception, the following tasks are offered, for example: observe the events and characters, express your attitude to them, express your impressions. These tasks are based on children's emotions and their understanding of the actual content of the work. During secondary perception, after the text is read again, students explain their understanding of the characters and events, their attitude to what they have read, reason, prove, and reflect [19].

Next, work is organized based on the children's creative imagination when perceiving the work: they imagine the characters, events, try to "see" them (the appearance of the characters, the place of action); explain the behavior, emotional state of the hero; think and confirm with words from the text how the author treats him, how we find out about this, etc.

Since a work has not only content but also form, special tasks are provided to identify the features of a fable, fairy tale, poem (as genres), to establish their similarities and differences, as well as to understand the features of the language of the work, its composition (construction). It is important that students understand how the work they are reading is constructed, what is achieved by this, what words the author chooses to depict the character, how they characterize this character.

The work on the work is completed by expressive reading, which is specially prepared by the teacher. It is very important for children to understand that there can be different versions of expressive reading, since it reflects different perceptions of the same work of art by people[9].

All tasks in the textbook are aimed at developing the students' learning activities. Children must: 1) understand the learning task (what needs to be done and why), 2) understand (think) how to complete the task, and 3) monitor and evaluate their work.

What is the content of the work in each section of the textbook, in what sequence is it carried out? Let's show this using the example of studying a fairy tale. This is not new material for students. Turning to it in the third grade allows you to deepen children's knowledge of folk art, teach them to distinguish between the genres of literary works, and also to see the poetry and diversity of the creativity of Russian people, the richness of Russian language[7].

At first, students are given information about the fairy tale, its sources, genre features, leading ideas (the triumph of good over evil, the affirmation of moral norms of life, the people's ideas about happiness, human dignity, etc.). It is important, without violating the poetic nature of the fairy tale, to show children that fairy tales combine the real and unreal worlds, and all the heroes are divided into positive and negative. The tasks suggest evaluating the actions of the heroes, paying attention to the special manner of their description, the folk language, the presence of repetitions, sayings, introductions, etc.

The next stage of work is the formation of ideas about the fact that the plots of many fairy tales are similar, although they differ in the manner of presentation, in how they were created at different times, in different places and told by different storytellers.

Children compare fairy tales with similar plots, become familiar with fairy tales that include riddles and heroes who defeat enemies not by force, but by wisdom, intelligence and ingenuity. Fairy tales-riddles are also studied in comparison [8].

And finally, we consider a fairy tale as a source of the writer's creativity. Folk and author's tales are often similar in plot and are studied in comparison. In the first and second grades, children have mastered free and selective retelling. In the third grade, they begin learning retelling and storytelling, which preserve the artistic features of the text. It is advisable to start with retelling individual episodes so that you can preserve (and therefore notice) all the expressive means of language (epithets, comparisons, personifications, etc.), and also convey the intonation pattern of the text, which allows you not only to understand the author's point of view, but also to express your own attitude to what is being read.

How to organize teaching artistic retelling? This work should be carried out when students have already mastered the content of the work, made a plan, highlighted the features of each episode. Considering that the works for reading in the third grade are quite voluminous, 2-3 lessons are allocated for their study. For teaching artistic storytelling, it is more appropriate to involve fairy tales. After reading a fairy tale, discussing it, you should work on the form of presentation and the plan. Together with the students, determine what content can be filled in each point of the plan, how to convey the mood of each character during retelling, which author's words should be completely preserved during retelling and why.

Children's literature developed from year to year. By the 1930s, it had its own professional poets and writers. Children's artists grew up in the field of poetry (Zafar Diyor, Adham Rakhmat, Ilyas Muslim, Shukur Sadulla, Sultan Jora, Mahmuda Akilova, Quddus Muhammadi), prose (Majid Fayzi, Dorjia Oppokova, Hakim Nazir) and Dorji Orji. Sadriddin Aini, Gafur Gulam, Hamid Olimjon, Oybek, Shokir Sulaimon, Elbek and Gairatiy) also contributed to the development of Uzbek children's literature. During this period, Zafar Diyor's collections of works were published: Songs (1933), Ceremony (1936), Poems (1939), Blessing (1940), Poems and Stories (1940), and the poem The Machinist (1935), the drama Happy Youth, and the stories Dispatch and Unhappy; A. Rahmat's books: Dum (1938), Happy Youth (1939), Pleasant Gods (1940), Poems (1940), and The Sly Fox (1940); Sultan Jora's Fidokor (1940); Ilyas Muslim's Growth (1932), Poisoners (1932), and Mikti Keldi (1934); Shukur Sadullah's "The Scream" (1933) was published[11].

During this period, many works of literature of fraternal peoples were translated into Uzbek. As a result, Uzbek children's literature became richer in all respects. In particular, the launch of such publications as "Young Turkestans", "Children's Comrade", "Children's World", "Changing Youth", "Young Force" led to the comprehensive development of children's literature.

Artistic retelling allows not only to assimilate the content of the work well, but also to see the features of its construction, notice unusual words, convey dialogues, imagine the characters and their relationships. Observations on the artistic features of the fairy tale are carried out in the process of working with the text.

Such work with the text is necessary to reveal the image of the fairy tale hero: description of his appearance, actions, attitude to other characters. It makes students listen attentively, read

attentively, look closely at the author's text in order to understand what the author wanted to say and determine their attitude to the heroes and the whole work.

In the third grade, children not only learn that fairy tales are about animals, everyday life and magic, but also observe their form (fairy tales-riddles, fairy tales in prose and in verse; riddles based on the opposition of phenomena and objects, riddles-questions, riddles based on specific features) [8].

When studying fairy tales, it is advisable to use diagrams, tables and crosswords. In the course of literary reading, this is a form of independent work of students, which is introduced to generalize the knowledge gained, increase reading vigilance, and cultivate attention to the word.

Tasks of this type are best completed in groups, which include children with different levels of training.

There are no special methods for diagnosing the level of mastering and analyzing fairy tales, so you can conduct a survey.

Thus, Abdulla Aripov's poem "The Story of the Farmer's Grandfather and Twelve Children" is one of the most significant achievements of Uzbek children's literature in recent years. There are many works about Uzbekistan in Uzbek children's poetry. A. Aripov wrote unique original works without repeating them. The main characters of the poem are excellent students from twelve provinces. They know the history of their place. They answer the questions of the grandfather who accompanied them on the train. Each region of Uzbekistan has its own riches, cities and generous people [11].

Thus, the results of the study allowed us to draw the following conclusions. Fairy tales have a huge pedagogical and educational value. They form stable folk ideas about the moral principles of life, are a visual school of the amazing art of words. Fairy tales contribute to the development of children's imagination and literary and creative abilities. Studying fairy tales increases the interest and motivation of schoolchildren to study literature. A fairy tale instills love for one's land and people. It forms the communicative qualities of younger schoolchildren.

Relying on folklore traditions, such a pedagogical task as the formation of a creatively developed personality of a schoolchild is solved. Various components of folk artistic culture have a powerful creative potential. And, of course, the possibilities of a fairy tale in developing children's creative abilities are obvious. The meaningful world of a fairy tale, its poetics and composition are close and accessible to children. Therefore, the use of a fairy tale in various types of creative activity opens up broad horizons for the formation of a creative personality.

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